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Abstract: UHTCs are the most suitable materials for space and hypersonic, however in service they lose their properties owing to oxidation damages. Tailoring composition and microstructure on a multiscale level may maintain structural stability in the sub-layers. Sintering of ZrB₂-MoSi₂ ceramics at 1900-2150°C results in microstructures characterized by partial or complete (Zr,Mo)B₂ solid solutions. This has notable impacts on the performance of the composites subjected to cyclic oxidation at 1650°C. Coupled XRD, SEM and TEM analyses pointed out the formation of a unique interpenetrating microstructure, where ZrO₂ micro-grains encase stable nano-sized MoB particles. This architecture manifested its suitability during repeated oxidation limiting the effect of oxygen attack to some microns thickness, due to diffused Mo which prevented turbulence and bursting phenomena on the outer glass. This study elucidates the processing conditions that lead to the development of prominent materials for application in new generation thermal protection systems for reusable space components.

Method to improve the oxidation resistance of ZrB₂-based ceramics for reusable space systems

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ABSTRACT

UHTCs are the most suitable materials for space and hypersonic, however in service they lose their properties owing to oxidation damages. Tailoring composition and microstructure on a multiscale level may maintain structural stability in the sub-layers. Sintering of ZrB₂-MoSi₂ ceramics at 1900-2150°C results in microstructures characterized by partial or complete (Zr,Mo)B₂ solid solutions. This has notable impacts on the performance of the composites subjected to cyclic oxidation at 1650°C. Coupled XRD, SEM and TEM analyses pointed out the formation of a unique interpenetrating microstructure, where ZrO₂ micro-grains encase stable nano-sized MoB particles. This architecture manifested its suitability during repeated oxidation limiting the effect of oxygen attack to some microns thickness, due to diffused Mo which prevented turbulence and bursting phenomena on the outer glass.

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1. Introduction

One of the main technological advances required in aerospace industry is the development of reusable space systems (RSS), namely the design of components and materials that should not change their shape, size, aerodynamic and thermal protection properties as a consequence of the various physical, chemical and structural solicitations throughout the entire operation period. The benefits of RSS include the reduction of the high maintenance costs and

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an increased reliability and durability, provided that they are able to tolerate some level of external damage without requiring repair [1-3].

In this perspective, the development of innovative materials for the fabrication of new generation thermal protection systems for future reusable space components would provide an answer to this demand.

The class of materials commonly termed as ultra-high temperature ceramics (UHTCs) has been indicated as the most potential candidate to constitute parts of such RSS in view of their melting point exceeding 3000°C and excellent ablation resistance as compared to SiC [3-5]. However, pure monolithic ceramics, like ZrB₂ or HfB₂, are not actually serviceable due to a series of limitations, like difficult ability to densify, poor damage tolerance and a critical oxidation resistance. In particular, the oxidation behaviour of borides has been thoroughly studied and modelled over a wide temperature range [6-7]. According to reaction (1), ZrB₂ oxidizes yielding porous ZrO₂ crystals and glassy B₂O₃. This last is liquid and partially protective up to 1000°C, but above, its volatilization leaves the porous scale fully susceptible to further oxygen attack, therefore the introduction of secondary phases that limit this and the above mentioned shortcomings is mandatory.

SiC phase, in form of particles, platelets or fibres, has proved to strongly enhance the thermo-mechanical properties of borides, thanks to the promotion of a refined microstructure [8-10] and triggering of toughening mechanisms [11-12], but one of the major impacts has been manifested in a notable increase of the oxidation resistance, owing to the development of a multi-layered architecture topped by a borosilicate glass upon oxidation [13-17], reaction (2). The critical aspect of SiC addition is however revealed above 1650°C, when active oxidation occurs in the subscale layers at the SiC-SiO₂ interface, owing to an unfavourable combination of low oxygen pressure and high temperature [18-19], reaction (3).

Other phases added to expand the operation limits of ZrB₂ include transition metals, in form of borides, carbides and silicides, in view of their capability of modifying the structure and oxygen permeability of glass and crystalline phases formed, i.e. SiO₂ and ZrO₂ [20-23]. It has been ascertained that, upon sintering, the introduction of transition metals Me, where Me =Ta, Mo, W or Cr, to ZrB₂ matrices promotes the formation of (Zr,Me)B₂ solid solutions that epitaxially grow around the original ZrB₂ nuclei [24]. The mechanism of formation of such substructures, generally known as “core-shell”, has been attributed to partial decomposition of the sintering additive containing the transition metal [24], for example, in the case of disilicides, reaction (4-5) have been proposed:

When silicides are employed, the mass transfer is favored and assisted by a transient liquid phase formed upon interaction of the oxides that naturally cover the starting powders (6), in which both Zr and Me are partially soluble:

Given the sharp interface between core and shell, without a diffusion gradient and often trapping Si-O-C particles [24-25], the shell structure is thought to be a consequence of re-precipitation mechanism from the liquid phase on the starting ZrB₂ cores upon cooling or when the solubility limit is achieved. Considering the same sintering temperature, ~1900°C, the amount of Me dissolved into the boride lattice mostly depends on the nature of the guest cation, found

1 to be 20 at% for Ta [25], below 10 at% for Mo [26] and 2 at% for W [27], however, recent results [28] have
2 demonstrated that the solubility limit can be augmented by an increase of the sintering temperature, that accelerates
3 the diffusion processes.

4 The way these core-shell structures evolve upon oxidation has been just disclosed and explained: ZrB_2
5 oxidizes into ZrO_2 which encases nano-inclusions whose nature depends on the oxygen and boron oxide relative
6 partial pressures in the specific subscale [29-30]. Although those studies pointed out the neat microstructure formed
7 and its effect on the capability to obstruct or enhance further oxygen permeation across the ZrO_2 scale, no
8 investigation has been undertaken to study the effect of the different amounts of the same transition metal dissolved
9 into the solid solution on the oxidation performances.
10

11 In this work, we present two ZrB_2 ceramics with initial 15 vol% $MoSi_2$ content hot pressed at two different
12 temperatures, 1900 and 2150°C, that promoted the evolution of two dissimilar composites with different amount of
13 Mo dissolved in the $(Zr,Mo)B_2$ solid solution. These differences were reflected on the oxidation response to cyclic tests
14 at 1650°C in dry air. The effect of Mo content on the oxidation behavior of the two UHTCs is discussed based on
15 microstructure evolution and thermodynamic computations.
16

17 The definition of the superiority of the mixed $(Zr,Mo)B_2$ solid solution over the pure ZrB_2 phase could provide a
18 potential design criterion for a new paradigm of ceramics with outstanding oxidation behaviour for application in
19 reusable space systems.
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21 **2. Experimental procedure**

22 **2.1 Materials processing**

23 15 vol% $MoSi_2$ was added to ZrB_2 to promote its densification and the following powders were used:
24 hexagonal ZrB_2 (Qinhuangdao Eno High-Tech Material Development Co., Ltd, China), purity>99.0%, impurities (wt%):
25 C<0.2, Hf<0.2, Fe<0.1, mean particle size range 0.5-1.0 μm ; tetragonal $MoSi_2$ (Qinhuangdao Eno High-Tech Material
26 Development Co., Ltd, China), purity>99.9%, impurities (wt%): Ti<0.014, Mn<0.0012, Co<0.0012, Zn<0.001,
27 Mg<0.0005, Sb<0.0003, mean particle size range 1.0-3.0 μm . Simultaneous grinding and mixing of the powders was
28 carried out in acetone in a planetary mill for 6 hours using WC-based grinding media. **No W-based compounds could be
29 detected in the starting powder.** The slurry was then dried using a rotary evaporator and finally sieved through 100 μm
30 screen, the average powder particle size after grinding did not exceed 2.5 μm .
31

32 Sintering was performed in two different hot pressing furnaces: **one at CNR-ISTEC and one at IPMS. In the first
33 case, labeled "A" later on, a green pellet, 30 mm in diameter and 10 mm height, was shaped by uniaxial pressing and
34 directly placed in the furnace and hot-pressed up to 1900°C in low vacuum (100 Pa) using an induction-heated graphite
35 die with an uniaxial pressure of 30 MPa and held at the maximum temperature for 20 minutes.**
36

37 In the second case, labeled "B", an 8 mm diameter and 10 mm height pellet was sintered in a vacuum hot pressing in
38 graphite molds. The nominal temperature on the outer surface of the mold was measured by an infrared thermometer
39 and the actual temperature inside the mold was calculated on the basis of specific calibrating plots. The actual
40 temperature achieved for the densification in case B was 2150°C with an applied mechanical pressure of 48 MPa, held
41 for 10 minutes. Free cooling followed in both cases.
42

43 **2.2 Oxidation test**

1 The resistance to oxidation was studied using a bottom-loading furnace with MoSi₂ heating elements
2 (Nannetti FC18, Faenza, Italy) exposing rectangular coupons 10.0 x 6.0 x 3.0 mm³ for 15 minutes to the effect of
3 stagnant air at 1650°C. The coupons, previously cleaned in acetone and weighed, were placed onto porous zirconia
4 supports, previously carved to limit the contact between the two surfaces, so that the coupons touched the zirconia
5 support only at the edges. The ceramic specimens were bottom-up loaded into the hot zone of the furnace when the
6 target temperature was achieved, elapsed 15 minutes and rapidly down-loaded from the hot chamber and let quench
7 in air. This oxidation cycle was repeated 3 times for a total duration of 45 minutes at 1650°C.
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10 11 12 **2.3 Materials characterization**

13 The final density of the two pellets was measured by the Archimedes' method in distilled water.

14 Crystalline phases of the as-sintered and oxidized ceramics were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD, mod. D8
15 Advance - Bruker, Germany) with Cu K α radiation, step size of 0.02 and 0.5 s counting rate in the 20-130° 2-Theta
16 range.
17

18 The microstructure before and after oxidation was analyzed on fractured and polished cross-sections by field-
19 emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM, mod. ΣIGMA, ZEISS NTS GmbH, Germany) coupled to an energy
20 dispersive X-ray micro-analyzer (EDS, mod. INCA Energy 300, Oxford Instruments, UK). Key microstructural features like
21 residual porosity, mean grain size and volumetric content of the secondary phases were evaluated from FESEM
22 micrographs elaborated with the support of the commercial software package Image Pro Plus (v.7, Media Cybernetics,
23 USA).
24

25 The sample for TEM analyses was prepared by cutting a disc from sample A upon oxidation. The disc was
26 mechanically ground down to about 20 μm and then further ion beam thinned until incipient perforations were
27 observed by optical microscope. Local phase analysis was performed using a transmission electron microscope (TEM,
28 JEOL JEM 2100F) operating at a nominal voltage of 200 kV and equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray system (EDS,
29 mod. INCA Energy 300, Oxford instruments, UK). Electron diffraction patterns identification was carried out through
30 the software tool developed for Digital Micrograph [31].
31

32 Thermodynamics and phase stability diagrams were computed by means of the commercial package HSC
33 Chemistry v. 6.12 (Outokumpu research Oy, Pori, Finland).
34

35 **3. Results and Discussion**

36 **3.1 As-sintered microstructure**

37 Table I summarizes the main processing conditions and resulting microstructural features of the two ZrB₂-
38 MoSi₂ ceramics that will be discussed in the following.
39

40 X-ray diffraction analysis revealed that in material A the boride peaks result split, demonstrating that the
41 nominally pure ZrB₂ is still present together with a new (Zr,Mo)B₂ solid solution with contracted unit cell parameters
42 due to the substitution of Mo, with smaller ionic radius (1.36 Å), into Zr sites, with larger ionic radius (1.60 Å), in
43 agreement with previous studies on borides sintered in presence of transition metal silicides or carbides [24]. On the
44 contrary, in material B, all peaks corresponding to ZrB₂ are shifted to higher 2-Theta angles indicating the formation of
45 one single solid solution.
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1 A zoomed portion of the x-ray diffraction patterns of the as sintered ceramics displaying the peaks splitting or
 2 shift is shown in Fig. 1. The table inset reports the lattice constants of the reference pure diboride phases, ZrB₂ and
 3 MoB₂, together with those of the two (Zr,Mo)B₂ solid solutions. An estimation of the Mo at% in each solid solution by
 4 Vegard's rule led to a (Zr_{0.98}Mo_{0.02})B₂ phase in material A and (Zr_{0.88}Mo_{0.12})B₂ in material B, in agreement with the
 5 different sintering temperatures experienced. The composition of these new solid solution is just indicative, since
 6 peak shifting could be due also to residual stresses arose in the sintered bulks upon cooling, due to the different
 7 coefficient of thermal mismatch of the composing phases. The main thing to notice here is the notably different Mo
 8 content in the two solid solutions passing from a sintering temperature of 1900°C to 2150°C, ~2 at% compared to ~12
 9 at%, respectively. Secondary phases include hexagonal SiC and traces of tetragonal MoB, more pronounced in
 10 material A. In none of the ceramics, residual MoSi₂ was detected.

11 A - Images of the microstructure of material A are displayed in Fig. 2a-c. Fig. 2a shows an overall view of the
 12 polished section: no major defects or residual porosity can be observed, two secondary phases can be identified: a
 13 dark contrasted one, SiC with SiO₂ pockets at the edges, and a bright one in the same amount, with irregular shape
 14 and low dihedral angles, Fig. 2b,c and Table I. EDS pointed out this to be MoB with W traces, owing to impurity take
 15 up during milling. The formation of SiC and SiO₂ can be explained following reaction (7), which also leaves notable
 16 amount of free Mo:

18 MoB phase is commonly observed in the ZrB₂-MoSi₂ system [24,28] and it derives from the reaction between MoSi₂
 19 and the oxides that naturally cover the starting ZrB₂ powders [32], reaction (8):

21 The matrix grains are rounded with average dimensions of 1.9 μm, different grey levels are due to different grains
 22 orientation. Fig. 3a-b discloses the morphology of the matrix: the core is ZrB₂, whilst the outer darker region, the rim,
 23 is ZrB₂ containing 6 at% of Mo, as the EDS spectra demonstrates with the tiny peak at 2.3 keV. The discrepancy with
 24 the Mo amount estimated by X-ray diffraction, 2 at%, is certainly due to the low quantity dissolved in the solid
 25 solution of material A, within the experimental error of the diffractometer. Given the precision of the two techniques,
 26 we consider the value obtained by EDS more reliable.

27 Occasionally residual MoSi₂ is found, but its amount can be negligible, below 1 vol%. The amounts of the secondary
 28 phases formed, MoB and SiC, are in agreement with the complete decomposition of MoSi₂ according to reaction (8).

29 B - An overview of the microstructure of material B is displayed in the SEM images of Fig. 2d-f, the grey phase
 30 is the newly formed (Zr,Mo)B₂ compound and the dark phase is a combination of SiC, B₄C and silica-based glass. The
 31 matrix grains are slightly elongated, with the longest axis between 5-7 μm and aspect around 1.8. EDS elemental
 32 mapping shows that Mo is homogeneously dispersed in the boride matrix and its distribution is not overlapped with
 33 that of Si, Fig. 3c, confirming complete MoSi₂ dissociation. The amount of Mo dissolved in the solid solution is now 12
 34 at%, Fig. 3d, in perfect agreement with the estimation from the x-ray diffraction pattern. The volume fraction of the
 35 dark phase is notably in higher amount and different shape as compared to material A, around 21 vol%. SiC grains,
 36 with maximum length of 3-5 μm, are characterized by elongated shape with aspect ratio around 3 and their shape
 37 indicates the presence of only the α polytype. Its relative amount is estimated to be around 15 vol% by image analysis,
 38 whilst the residual 6 vol%, with irregular profiled shape, is mostly SiO₂ pockets and B₄C, Fig. 2b. SiO₂ is a residual of

MoSi₂ dissociation, whilst B₄C is a product formed upon sintering owing to the high carbon mobility at the elevated temperatures during hot pressing.

3.2 Microstructure upon oxidation

A photo of the oxidized samples after 3 cycles of 15 minutes at 1650°C is reported in the inset of Fig. 4. The aspect of the UHTCs after three cycles did not notably vary in case B, where just some shiny covering can be seen due to glass formation, whilst bubbling and little whitening is observed for material A. However, no delamination or spallation of the external oxide occurred in any material. The specific weight gain was in both cases negligible, higher after the first cycle, 0.2-0.3%/cm², and stable after the second and third ones, below 0.1%/cm².

The x-ray diffraction patterns recorded on the surface of the specimens after cyclic oxidation are reported in Fig. 4. As expected, the main crystalline phase is monoclinic ZrO₂ with traces of tetragonal MoB in material A. Astonishingly, in material B, ZrB₂ is retained as main crystalline phase and only little traces of monoclinic ZrO₂ and MoB are found.

SEM images of the external surfaces reported in Fig. 5, show that both materials are covered by a continuous silica-based glass with crystalline bright precipitates. Some bubbling phenomena occurred, especially in sample A. The surface of material A is in general rougher and no Mo is detected within the white crystalline precipitates, Fig. 5a,b. This can be due to the low amount of Mo dissolved in the solid solution of material A, resulting in small and few Mo-based inclusions. In addition, ZrO₂ aggregates located in larger SiO₂-rich area with different contrast glass surrounding the aggregates are commonly found and can be associated to the convection cells described in [33]. The aspect of the outer surface of material B is smooth and regular, Fig. 5c. Silica glass does not contain foreign cations, nor Zr, nor Mo, Fig. 5d. Higher magnification images of the bright precipitates in material B evidence the formation of tiny bright rounded particles homogeneously dispersed on the surface of ZrO₂ grains, Fig. 5e-f. These contain Mo-B and have variable diameter between 50 and 180 nm.

The cross sections of the oxidized samples are reported in the SEM images of Fig. 6. As first observation, it can be remarked the excellent oxidation resistance of material B, where less than 20 μm of outer SiO₂ glassy phase effectively protected the bulk, as no ZrO₂ layer can be delineated, Fig. 6a,c.

Material A allowed the oxidation of a thicker portion of material, ~60 μm. Similar to other ZrB₂-based ceramics, material A shows a multilayered architecture. Two main scales and two interfaces of the volume interested by the oxidation attack are identified, Fig. 6b. A continuous surface silica scale, labeled SZ, about 20 μm thick embeds ZrO₂ grains and agglomerates, Fig. 6b. Moving towards the ceramic core, a 40 μm thick and dense ZrO₂-based layer, ZSM, containing MoSi₂ oxidation products, namely SiO₂ and MoB, is found before the un-oxidized bulk. It can be noticed that the repeated oxidation progressively induced the migration of silica close to the upper surface, indicating that at this temperature silica is very fluid. In addition, Fig. 6b displays the morphology of MoB and SiO₂ phases adjacent to each other and well dispersed in the ZSM layer. A magnified picture of ZrO₂ grains at the SZ/ZSM interface in the inset of Fig. 6b evidences that silica glass fills the interstitials among ZrO₂ growing grains and MoB large particles are located up to the SZ/ZSM interface, suggesting a critical variation of partial pressure at this depth. Furthermore, an intra-granular nano-sized structure, characterized by bright contrasts and rounded shape, is found encased and decorating ZrO₂ grains. TEM investigations allowed a more precise definition of the nature of such inclusions. Fig. 7a displays the overall appearance of ZrO₂ grains encasing dispersed particles and connected by dislocations. In Fig.7b

1 the lamella growing planes associated to the tetragonal-to-monoclinic phase transformation of ZrO_2 [34] are well
2 visible, whilst Fig. 7c-d show high resolution images of MoB particles with the corresponding diffraction pattern and
3 EDS spectra. Given the tiny size of the inclusions, 10-20 nm, both signals about crystallinity and chemistry are
4 overlapped to that of ZrO_2 , Fig. 7e-f. Similar intra-granular nanostructured morphology was observed upon oxidation
5 of $(Zr,W)B_2$ and $(Zr,Ta)B_2$ solid solutions [29-30].

6
7 In material B, at the silica/bulk interface, MoB phase is systematically found immersed in the glass and in
8 form of nano-aggregates and platelets, Fig. 6e. Underneath, the $(Zr,Mo)B_2$ solid solution and SiC remained unaffected
9 by oxygen attack.
10

11 **3.3 Sintering behavior**

12 From the microstructures just presented, Table I, and from previous investigations on this system [24], a general
13 sintering mechanism can be drawn. A schematic of the microstructure evolution upon sintering and after oxidation of
14 the two ceramics is sketched in Fig. 8.
15

16 $MoSi_2$ is not stable at high temperature in vacuum and tends to dissociate into Si and Mo [24]. The first is
17 liquid above 1400°C, which is close to the temperature at which shrinkage is recorded and runs along the boride
18 particles cleaning them from the covering oxides, ZrO_2 and B_2O_3 , thus making the boride powder more reactive to
19 sinter. Mo is then dissolved in a Si-Mo-Zr-B-O transient liquid phase which favors densification [35]. When the
20 sintering is performed at 1900°C, upon cooling, an epitaxial $(Zr,Mo)B_2$ solid solution precipitates on the original ZrB_2
21 nuclei, MoB crystallizes with residual SiO_2 glassy phase. As a consequence of the high carbon mobility at the sintering
22 temperatures, from dies and rams, silica is carbo-reduced to SiC phase.
23

24 In material B, at increased sintering temperature, 2150°C, $MoSi_2$ is completely dissociated as well and Mo is fully
25 encased into a new single $(Zr,Mo)B_2$ solid composing the matrix. MoB is not present, since residual oxide phases are
26 reduced owing to the increased carbon diffusivity above 2000°C. In addition, SiC has a platelet-like shape, implying the
27 presence of only α polytype.
28

29 The observation of only SiC in material B, whilst a combination of equal volume fraction of SiC and MoB in material A
30 suggests that at low temperature, case A, reaction (8) is more favorable, whilst at higher temperature, case B, reaction
31 (7) prevails, in agreement with thermodynamic computations. The plot in Fig. 9a shows the free Gibbs energy
32 calculated at atmospheric pressure[†] as a function of the sintering temperature for reactions (7) and (8) and, indeed,
33 there is an inversion of the favorability of occurrence at around 1600°C. It has to be underlined that both hot pressings
34 were performed in vacuum, therefore the discrepancy between the actual and calculated cross temperature could be
35 attributed to a different pressure inside the hot pressing chamber.
36

37 **3.4 Oxidation behavior**

38 In order to correlate the different oxidation behaviors of the two nominal identical composites, one has to keep in
39 mind the main microstructural differences resulted from two different sintering temperatures, 1900°C for material A
40 and 2150°C for material B, Fig. 8. Therefore, the discussion will focus on the effect of three major aspects: i) the type
41 and amount of secondary phases, ii) the chemistry of the matrix and iii) the grain size of the matrix.
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61 [†] The software used, HSC Chemistry v. 6.12, allows this type of calculations only at atmospheric pressure.
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1 i) The first issue regards the secondary phase. MoSi₂ in both cases is completely dissociated upon
2 densification and not detected any more in the microstructure, nor by XRD nor by SEM-EDS. However, due to the
3 different sintering temperatures, 7 vol% of MoB and 7 vol% of SiC are found in ceramic A, whilst 15 vol% of SiC is
4 present in material B. What follows from different type and amount of secondary phases is the quantity of liquid SiO₂
5 phase produced upon oxidation, following reactions (2) or (9), and also the composition of the formed glass, that may
6 have different viscosity, influenced by a different cations content, owing to the capturing of Mo from reaction (10):
7

12 The free Gibbs energy of reactions (9) and (10) calculated at 1650°C, atmospheric pressure and normalized with
13 respect to the moles of oxygen is -126 and -121 kcal, respectively, indicates that SiC is the phase oxidizing first and
14 able to form a continuous protective silica layer on the surface. In this respect, material B will display a better
15 oxidation protection as compared to A, firstly due to higher amount of SiC.
16
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18 Given the lack of data on viscosity of borosilicate glass containing Zr and Mo dissolved and in the temperature
19 of interest, considerations on the glass are done just in a speculative way. B₂O₃ is highly volatile at 1650°C and it is
20 therefore supposed to immediately evaporate once it achieves the surface. As a matter of fact, chemical analysis
21 performed on the outer glass by SEM-EDS did not evidence substantial compositional differences between material A
22 and B, suggesting either a poor Mo solubility into silica and/or a rapid evaporation of MoO₃ at 1650°C. It has been
23 reported that convection cells on the surface are formed from ZrO₂ precipitates from a boron-silica-zirconia oxide
24 liquid that forms upon oxidation above 1550°C, and glass with larger SiO₂/B₂O₃ ratio will dissolve less ZrO₂ [34].
25 Therefore, higher SiC-containing ZrB₂-composites, like material B, present less dissolved ZrO₂ because they have more
26 SiO₂ available, which results in a smaller amount of precipitated ZrO₂ and fewer convection cells.
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29 The more pronounced bubbling activity observed on the surface of material A, Fig. 5a, indicates the
30 formation of more or just more localized gaseous species in the subsurface layer, these may include B₂O₃, SiO and
31 MoO₃. However, boron oxide amount is equally present in the two materials given the same boride matrix; SiO_(g)
32 forms at the SiC/SiO₂ interface at oxygen partial pressure below 10⁻¹¹ Pa, i.e. lower than the actual region right
33 underneath the silica shield where bubbling is observed [36]; at last gas formation close to the surface is likely to be
34 attributed to MoO₃, which is reported to vaporize accompanied by “important gas turbulence” [37]. Since the initial
35 Mo-amount is the same in the two materials, the most probable hypothesis is related to a different distribution of
36 Mo-cations and hence of volatile Mo-oxides: in A it is present both as discrete phase, MoB, and distributed
37 throughout the boride matrix within the solid solution, instead in B, Mo is just homogeneously encased into the
38 boride matrix. Therefore, we suppose that where MoB large aggregates are present in high concentration close to the
39 surface, higher amount of localized MoO₃ will be developed, thus provoking bursting in silica glass.
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42 ii) Concerning the matrix, in the first case pure ZrB₂ is still present together with a (Zr,Mo)B₂ solid
43 solution containing almost halved amount of atomic Mo as compared to the solid solution formed in material B,
44 where it is a continuous and homogeneous matrix. The main implication of these differences regards the distribution
45 of Mo oxidation products within the boride matrix. The matter if pure ZrB₂ is more oxidation resistant than Mo-doped
46 ZrB₂ cannot be solved by thermodynamics, due to the lack of fundamental input data in commercial software of such
47 mixed compounds, therefore it will be treated in a speculative way.
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SEM-EDS analysis confirmed by TEM investigations demonstrated that the oxidation of the solid solution results in ZrO₂ encasing MoB nano-inclusions, Fig. 7, following an overall reaction path that can be summarized in (11):

The oxidation of the boride phases releases significant amounts of B₂O₃, which is gaseous at 1650°C and therefore plays a fundamental role in changing the overall partial pressures and in the formation of condensed phases in the sublayers. In this respect, the complex reactivity environment in the subsurface scales, at a lower oxygen partial pressure than on the outermost surface, can be represented through the phase stability diagrams calculated at 1650°C for the Zr-B-O and Mo-B-O systems varying the oxygen and boron oxide partial pressure, Fig. 9b,c. Looking at the shaded areas in the plots of Fig. 9b,c, we notice that at 1650°C, from 10⁻¹⁰ to 10⁻¹³ atm of oxygen partial pressures, the stable condensed phases are ZrO₂ in the Zr-B-O system and MoB and Mo in the Mo-B-O system. This indicates that ZrO₂ is thermodynamically more stable than Mo-oxides, so that the limited amount of oxygen diffusing through the oxide scale is preferentially captured by the Zr-containing phases, and will leave solid MoB/Mo un-oxidized. However, moving to higher oxygen partial pressures, Mo is unavoidably lost by sublimation as oxide [37]. This explains why MoB is detected only up to the SZ/ZSM interface and not anymore in SZ layer, see Fig. 6b.

According to the microstructure analysis and available thermodynamics, we conclude that a material containing Mo homogeneously distributed in a boride matrix, i.e. fully dissolved in the (Zr,Mo)B₂ solid solution, will generate a smoother oxidized surface due to limited bubbling phenomena that intensify oxygen penetration through the bulk.

The choice of cation to be dissolved into the boride matrix has a paramount importance. As long as the nano-inclusions nestled into ZrO₂ are located at oxygen partial pressure below 10⁻¹⁰-10⁻¹² Pa, they are stable as solid compounds. However, above this pressure threshold one has to consider the oxide that they will form and in which state this will be. For example, according to studies performed on the ZrB₂ containing Ta or W [29-30], it resulted well evident that the evolution of the encased particles to solid Ta₂O₅, accompanied by a large volume expansion, or to gaseous WO_x, respectively, was fatal for the disruption or preservation of the ZrO₂ solid structure, respectively.

iii) Finally, the grain size of the two materials is notably different, around 2 μm for the material sintered at the lowest temperature and around 5-7 μm for the material sintered at the highest temperature. This factor may have an impact on the oxygen diffusion along grain boundaries. Although the ZrO₂-based scale in material A looks compact, it is noticeable that silica veins regularly run along the grain boundary. The oxygen diffusion across amorphous silica, that likely contains dissolved boron too [38] is higher than the diffusion across crystalline ZrO₂ [39-40]. Therefore also this feature may have contributed to the higher oxidation degree of material A.

4. Conclusions

A ZrB₂ - 15 vol% MoSi₂ powder mixture was sintered to full density at two temperatures, 1900 and 2150°C, resulting in notably different microstructural features. The lowest temperature induced the formation of core-shell grains in the boride matrix, where the core is ZrB₂ and the shell a (Zr_{0.94}Mo_{0.06})B₂ solid solution and, of the initial MoSi₂ content, 7 vol% of MoB phase was found together with 7 vol% of SiC as a consequence of the silicide dissociation and reaction within reducing atmosphere. At higher temperature, the matrix evolved instead into a continuous solid solution with higher Mo content dissolved in the solid solution, (Zr_{0.88}Mo_{0.12})B₂, and about 15 vol% of SiC phase with platelet shape.

1 The oxidation resistance at 1650°C for 15 minutes and repeated three times evidenced the superior
2 performances of the material sintered at 2150°C owing to a combination of favorable factors:

- 3 i) higher SiC content, able to provide an outermost stable silica-based layer;
4
5 ii) a diffused Mo supply from the solid solution, which evolves into an architecture organized on a multi-scale
6 level where ZrO₂ grains encase solid and stable MoB nano-inclusions and limit turbulence or bursting
7 phenomena on the surface glass due to development of volatile MoO₃;
8
9 iii) a coarser grain size that notably reduces the oxygen permeability along the grain boundaries through the
10 borosilicate glassy phase.
11

12 This study outlined the importance of an appropriate processing route to obtain ceramic composites suitable for
13 application in reusable space systems, thus opening a new path to the design of materials with exceptional oxidation
14 performances at ultra-high temperatures and with long-lasting usability in service.
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21 oxidation tests.
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Tables

Material	Sintering, °C, MPa, min	porosity, %	Phases upon sintering, vol%	Mo dissolved into ZrB ₂ , at%	Matrix m.g.s.
A	1900, 30, 20	<1	(Zr,Mo)B ₂ , ZrB ₂ , 7 MoB, 7 SiC, 2SiO ₂	6	1.9±0.7
B	2150, 48, 10	<1	(Zr,Mo)B ₂ , 15 SiC, 3 B ₄ C, 3 SiO ₂	12	4.1±1.5

Table I: Summary of the processing conditions and microstructural features upon sintering of the two ZrB₂-15 vol% MoSi₂ composites.

Fig. 1: X-ray diffraction patterns of materials A and B showing peaks splitting in the first and peaks shift in the second one. The table inset lists the calculated lattice parameters for the two solid solutions and the amount of Mo dissolved, as estimated from Vegard's rule.

Fig. 2: SEM images showing the microstructure of material A (a-c) and B (d-f).

Fig. 3: a) SEM image showing microstructural details in material A with the corresponding b) EDS spectra of core and rim phases. c) SEM image of material B with elemental distribution of Zr, Mo and Si with d) EDS spectra of the (Zr,Mo)B₂ solid solution superimposed to that of pure ZrB₂.

Fig. 4: X-ray diffraction patterns of materials A and B upon cyclic oxidation showing the boride as main phase in the first and the oxide in the second one. The inset shows photos of the ceramics after the 3 oxidation cycles at 1650°C.

Fig. 5: a) SEM image of the oxidized surface of material A showing the overall appearance with EDS of pure ZrO₂ in b). c-f) SEM images of the oxidized surface of material B showing the c) overall appearance with SiO₂ glass and crystalline agglomerates and e) magnification of the ZrO₂ precipitates with Mo-B inclusions and d), f) corresponding EDS spectra.

Fig. 6: SEM images of the oxidized cross sections of materials a)-b) A and c)-e) B showing the different modified thickness and architecture. Tags in b) corresponds to different oxidized layers: SZ - SiO₂ glass embedding ZrO₂ aggregates, ZSM - ZrO₂ encasing MoSi₂ oxidation products, MoB and SiO₂. The inset in b) is a magnification of the SZ/ZSM interface evidencing bright nano-inclusions within ZrO₂ grains.

Fig. 7: TEM images of ZSM layer in material A showing a)-b) the overall appearance of ZrO_2 grains with nested nano-sized particles, c)-d) HR-TEM of such MoB inclusions, identified by e) diffraction pattern and f) EDS analysis. The spectrum of pure ZrO_2 is shown too, to discriminate the signal relative to MoB phase.

Fig. 8: Sketch of the different microstructures resulting from different hot pressing temperature and corresponding architecture of the oxidized scales.

Fig. 9: a) Free Gibbs energy, ΔG , measured for reactions (7) and (8) as a function of the sintering temperature showing that at high temperature reaction (7) is more favorable. Phase stability diagrams for the b) Zr-B-O and c) Mo-B-O systems as a function of oxygen and boron oxide partial pressures calculated at 1650 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The shaded areas evidence that the most stable compounds are different in the two systems under the same conditions of temperature and pressure, ZrO₂ versus MoB/Mo.

Figures captions

- 1
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37 temperature and pressure, ZrO_2 versus MoB/Mo.
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